

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

UZBEKISTAN AND EURASIAN ECONOMIC UNION (EEU) RELATIONSHIPS

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Abstract

In this article, it is considered that the inclusion of the Republic of Uzbekistan in regional integration societies and Eurasian economic integration will have positive effects on the effective use of labor, investment resources, and technologies, as well as corporate privileges, without compromising national sovereignty.

Keywords: single economic space, customs union, national sovereignty, post-Soviet area, supreme economic council, intergovernmental council, economic commission, preferential trade agreement.

Introduction.

Effective organization of economic activities, intensive development of international trade and economic relations, and active participation in globalization processes are crucial for ensuring economic growth and stability in the world market. Currently, regional cooperation relations are developing rapidly, and Uzbekistan is highly interested in participation in these processes and leverage the benefits of economic integration. Uzbekistan participates in economic associations such as MOHT, CIS, OIC and SCO, and its role and importance in their activities are increasing. Uzbekistan's entrance is a big consideration for the union as it has great influence and prestige in the region. Uzbekistan possesses abundant natural and agricultural resources, as well as significant industrial, scientific-technical, and technological potential. Active participation in regional integration processes can provide an opportunity to enter the global market of goods, services, labor, and capital, and address the weaknesses of the national economy, such as limited water and electricity resources. It is important to effectively utilize existing potential.

International regional integration can be seen as the practical implementation of the principle of 'globalization through regionalization', regardless of its format. This process can be compared to a multi-stage spaceship. The development and strengthening of the national economy is the first stage. The second stage involves the formation and development of integrated associations within the subregion. The third stage is the formation and development of integrated associations at a higher regional level. Finally, the fourth stage involves integration into the world economic structures.

This principle can be applied to developing and strengthening the military, political, and economic security systems within the region. It begins with enhancing national security and extends to the framework of regional and international security. In this context, regional security serves as a link connecting national and global security systems.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The theoretical and practical aspects of the development of economic integration processes are presented by the classics of economics A. Smith, D. Ricardo, D. S. Mill and J. B. Seylar, S. Harris, E. Heksher from the modern economists-scientists. B. Olin, P. Samuelson, S. Linder, V. Leontiev, M. Porter, F. Peru and G. Myrdal evaluated the international division of labor between countries, peoples and societies as the basis of economic integration [7. p. 203].

Problems of integration of national economies into the world economic system in the conditions of transition to market relations, issues of development of trade and economic relations and deepening of integration processes within the framework of CIS was studied by scientists of the CIS such as A. Kireyev, A. Yevdokimov, K. Semyonov, V. Shumilov, I. Faminsky, E. Avdokushin, V. Kolesov, V. Pokrovskaya, V. Sokolov, B. Fomin, Y. Shishkov, A. Elyanov.

V.M.Shumilov explains that "International economic integration is the process of unification of independent states in order to create an expanded economic area."

N.K. Isingarín evaluates international economic integration as the internationalization of the economic life of states and regions.

According to A. Popovich, "international economic integration" is the removal of economic borders between two or more national economies.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of these problems, as well as the problems of further development of trade and economic relations within the CIS during the integration of Uzbekistan into the world economic system, are presented by the economists of our republic: S. Gulomov, N. Tokhliyev [4, 5, 6, 7, 8], researched by D. Ahmedov, A. Abulkosimov, N. Sirajiddinov, B. Islamov, A. Bedrinsev, A. Ishmukhamedov, A. Isojonov, A. Rasulev, A. Alimov, E. Trushin, and others.

However, considering the recent trends in global economic relations, the legal and organizational aspects of developing trade and economic relations between CIS countries as a single customs union, and the primary methods of enhancing trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and the CIS countries are still

inadequate. The relevance of the chosen topic in this scientific article is determined by the fact that it has not been studied at this level.

The main part

Eurasian economic integration started in 2001-2014 with the establishment of the Eurasian Economic Community. The member states first established the Customs Union, followed by the Single Economic Space. The initial aim of the community was to modernise and cooperate national economies, increase their competitiveness, raise the standard of living of the population of participating countries, and create conditions for sustainable economic development. From January 1, 2015, a new stage in the life of the community began, with the Kyrgyz Republic and Armenia joining the association that was started as the Eurasian Economic Union by the countries of Kazakhstan, Russia, and Belarus. Since 2018, Moldova has signed agreements on the establishment of free trade zones with Vietnam, Iran, China, Cuba, and Serbia (as an observer). Agreements on entering free trade zones are being prepared with Egypt, Thailand, Mongolia, India, and Singapore. Around 50 countries, including Hungary, Israel, Cambodia, Laos, Pakistan, Peru, the Republic of Korea, Syria, Tunisia, Chile, Japan, and Indonesia, have expressed interest in cooperating with the EEU. The proposal put forward by Russian President V. Putin is to coordinate the activities of the EEU with regional organizations such as ASEAN and SCO, effectively turning it into an 'integration of integration'. This could potentially make the EEU the core of intercontinental integration. To achieve this, it is suggested that a number of national or interstate structures be formed to create a single economic space within the EEU framework.

Economic Commission;

Commission on raw material resources;

Commission on economic and scientific-technical cooperation;

Commission on international financial-industrial groups, joint ventures;

International Investment Bank;

International Arbitration;

Commission on settlement and currency introduction;

Commission on Ecology;

EEU court.

The project of Eurasian integration was first proposed in 1994 by the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, N. Nazarbayev. Some of these commissions are currently active. The proposal was sent to the leaders of the CIS countries and later distributed to the UN as an official document, which was subsequently published in the mass media. The project aimed to demonstrate that the CIS has not yet reached its full potential. However, the current structure of its bodies prevents the full utilization of its integration potential. Based on past experience, there is a need to move towards a new stage of integration. On 20th September 1994, the city of Alma-Ata hosted an international scientific and practical conference on the topic of Eurasian space: integration potential and its realization. The conference included speeches from N. Nazarbayev and the then Prime Minister of the Russian Federation, N. Ryzhkov,

as well as discussions on the necessity of Eurasian integration and the expected results. The language used throughout the conference was clear, objective, and value-neutral, with a formal register and precise word choice. The sentences and paragraphs created a logical flow of information with causal connections between statements. The text is free from grammatical errors, spelling mistakes, and punctuation errors. No changes in content were made as per the instructions.

In fact, Eurasia was not a new concept, but entered the scientific literature at the end of the 18th century. This idea was later developed in the works of famous Russian scientists N. Vernadsky and L. Gumilev. In particular, the next author showed the role of this space, which is considered the largest continent of the globe, in the formation and development of ethnic groups. In addition, both the USSR and the CIS were involved in this area. It was planned that this union would become the second full-fledged union in the world after the EU. However, there are also political problems between the member states. EEU is not a political association thus there should be no issues related to national sovereignty in the Union Treaty. It includes issues of economic cooperation, sovereign equality, consideration of national interests of member states, and equal rights.

Free movement of goods, services, capital and labor force are agreed or unified in the policy coordination in economic sectors, for example, in the fuel and energy sector, within the framework of the EEU.

It was agreed to move to the single rule of technical regulation of veterinary-sanitary and phytosanitary safety, to move the product across the territory of the member states under uniform requirements and equal conditions.

It was established that the citizens of the integrated countries can work in the member state of their choice without obtaining a permit, and it is possible to use the educational document without the recognition procedure. From May 6, 2017, the single market for medicines and medical supplies began to operate, from 2019, the transition to the single market for electricity began, and from 2025, the single market for oil and oil products will be launched. The Eurasian High Economic Council (Heads of State), the Eurasian Intergovernmental Council (Heads of Government) and the Eurasian Economic Commission are working regularly.

As an independent country, Uzbekistan actively participates in several international economic integration associations. In 2019, it became a full member of the Council of Turkic-speaking countries and worked towards an agreement for enhanced cooperation with the European Union. Some individuals demanded a national referendum on this matter, and emotions surrounding it were particularly intense for three years. There are differing opinions on the benefits of joining the EEU, with some arguing that it threatens political independence. However, a working group has been formed to study the issue and no well-thought-out calculations have been made on either side. While it is true that joining a regional organization may result in a loss of national powers, it also presents opportunities for integration and synergistic effects. The question remains: which option is preferable?

In Eurasia there is the CIS, the SCO, and the OCT. And on top of that, the Eurasian Economic Community. Isn't there so many platforms in one space, doesn't the Eurasian Union deny the CIS? Would not the relations between independent countries be weakened within its framework? Perhaps, instead of sticking to horizontal integration, vertical integration (participation in multinational corporations) should also be considered. Having passed the path of several decades of development, the EU has also taken the first steps of coal and steel integration!

The CIS was established in order to develop comprehensive economic cooperation in the post-Soviet space. Its main goal was to strengthen bilateral and multilateral traditional economic relations between the member countries. In addition, the wider the economic space for the free movement of labor, capital, goods and services in a market economy, the better. All the more harmful if their paths are blocked by different alliances. After all, why can some countries within the same union have customs tariffs and other benefits, while others should be an exception.

New aspects of economic integration are opening and one does not interfere with the other. Despite this, Alisher Kadyrov, one of the spokespersons of the political party in Uzbekistan, considers the Soviet Union to be "more sharply, it can be called the second USSR, it is a union with hidden economic and political goals in name only." True, he soon softened his harsh opinion. "The opposition took a radical approach to the issue of non-admission to the EEU as never before: joining the EEU means the end of political independence", "This action will be the beginning of the disappearance of Uzbekistan as an independent state", "what kind of economic relationship is an instrument of political relationship".

In this regard, political scientist Aziza Umarova is no exception. She called the entry into the EEU "Hello Soviet Union".

In fact, the equalization of EEU with the USSR belonged to another figure. In 2012, then US Secretary of State Hillary Clinton equated the Eurasian Union with the restoration of the USSR and called on her government to oppose the integration process in the territory of the former USSR.

In the article of Helsinki University researcher Sherzod Eraliyev entitled "Membership of the EEU is said to ease the life of migrants: the reality" many migrants from Kyrgyzstan, a member of the union, work without formalizing their activities. If Uzbekistan is also a member, 2 mln. 700,000 migrants can engage in informal activities without a patent. However, whether this can be a sufficient argument for entering the union or not, of course, no.

Alisher Umriddinov, a researcher at Nagoya University (Japan), believes that joining the union has the following advantages: a large market, notary barriers are reduced, favorable conditions are created for labor migrants, international relations based on rules are developed, opportunities for participation in the development process of EEU are expanded. Although the next two directions are more abstract, the above three directions are concrete and effective mechanisms. His opinion on labor migration completely refutes Sh. Eraliyev's argument. A. Umriddinov sees the negative aspects of joining the union as protectionist obstacles, the weak-

ness of the union as an organizational structure, the superiority of political will over the agreed rules, the limitation of sovereign rights in terms of external duties, and the underdevelopment of Russia, which created the EEU. As you can see, these situations are quite general, and the results are likely to happen in the future.

Based on these reasons, as an alternative way for Uzbekistan to conclude a free trade agreement with Vietnam, to deepen the existing free trade agreements with the countries of the CIS, to strengthen economic cooperation within the framework of the SCO, to focus on free trade cooperation between the countries of the CIS, suggests accelerating negotiations with the EU and the WTO before joining the EEU.

Sadiq Safoyev, the first deputy speaker of the upper house of the Parliament of Uzbekistan, tried to ease the tension by saying that he will not sign any agreement that harms the national interests of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, in the study organized by the "Center for Economic Research and Reforms" under the administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the topic of "Analysis of the consequences of Uzbekistan's membership in the EEU", very deep and clear opinions were put forward. According to the center's conclusion, "Uzbekistan's membership in the EEU can remove obstacles to the access of national products to the markets of the Union countries and significantly reduce export-related costs for exporters. The expansion of the Union, the establishment of free trade zones by this organization with other countries will help Uzbek exports to enter the market of these countries." Also, it will be beneficial for Uzbek business, wide opportunities will be created for labor migrants, common customs definition will be applied, the country's industry will be modernized, export of horticulture and processed agricultural products, unnecessary demand and increases by removing obstacles, expands logistics and transport possibilities.

Excessive politicization of membership in the EEU closes the eyes of economic expediency, distances it from world experience, and distracts from the main path. According to the opinion of the side against this issue, the Eurasian economic space mainly serves Russia's political interests, and it is argued that its dominance will be established again during the integration. What, there is no Russia in the CIS? To whom is Russia transferring its judgment and will in the CIS?

From December 2020, Uzbekistan received the status of an observer state of the Eurasian Economic Union. Uzbekistan is a traditional strategic partner of the EEU, and the observer status allows to rise to a new stage of cooperation, which will not be devoid of benefits for both sides.

As an observer country, Uzbekistan signed a memorandum of cooperation with the Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) in Tashkent in April 2021, as well as a plan of joint activities for the next years. The memorandum covers trade policy, customs and technical regulation, protection of consumer rights, as well as social and labor rights of workers, pharmaceutical and medical supplies, financial market, transport, energy, industry and agriculture, tourism, digital economy. implies cooperation on

The observer status allows Uzbekistan to increase trade and economic cooperation with the five CEE countries. In 2021, the volume of trade between them

increased by 22.9% and amounted to 11.6 billion dollars, in 2022 it was 15.7 billion dollars, and in January-October 2023 it was 12.9 billion dollars.

Also, joining EEU will create equal conditions for labor migrants, create favorable conditions for access to the countries of Vietnam, Iran, Serbia and Singapore, which have the opportunity to use the investment resources and technologies of the Union, customs privileges, and lead to the development of mutual tourist flows.

70% of Uzbekistan's foreign trade and 90% of foreign labor migration go to the CIS member states. This is a sufficient reason to become a full-fledged member. If EEU 182 mln. consists of people, the gross domestic product is 2.6 trillion. If we take into account the fact that the dollar is a large market, the issue becomes clearer. Full and effective use of all opportunities in regional integration is the main issue. But here is another situation. Each international economic organization should include one or two countries with great power and resource potential, and it should unite capital, finance and technological forces around it. For example, in NAFTA, the US controls the technology market, Mexico provides labor and Canada supplies raw materials. If Germany plays a leading role in the European Union, Japan will play such a role in ASEAN. Is there a country with such a role and importance in EEU? Can Russia play this role? Won't this international organization become an amorphous, difficult-to-manage association limited to offering only recommendations? For this, it is necessary to closely study the practice and experience of other international associations.

Conclusion.

One important trend in the current world economy is the increasing interdependence of national economies and the strengthening of regional and global integration. Regional integration is a deep socio-economic process and an external factor in the development of national economies. In the classical sense, this process involves the association of a group of countries located in the same geographical area, with similar levels and rates of development, and with common interests.

The Republic of Uzbekistan participates in various economic associations, including MOHT, CIS, IHT, and SCO. The country holds significant influence and prestige in the region. Currently, there is a debate regarding its admission to the EEU. In 2019, Uzbekistan became a member of the Turkic-speaking State Council and is working towards an agreement for expanded cooperation with the EU.

Active participation in regional integration processes enables effective utilization of existing potential, access to a wider market of goods and services, labour and capital, and addresses the weaknesses of the national economy, such as limited water and electricity resources and problems in the use of labour resources.

Considerable experience in regional integration has been gained worldwide. The majority of countries are members of regional economic blocs. Currently, successful international economic associations such as the EU, NAFTA, ASEAN, OPEC, SCO, and CIS are in operation.

Regionalization and globalization are not mutually exclusive; in fact, they are causally related. Regional integration creates the necessary conditions for globalization. Regional integration can act as a socio-

economic elevator, taking national economies to the world arena. Globalization, on the other hand, can pave the way for regionalization.

Transnational corporations and financial groups play a significant role in promoting regionalization and globalization. They connect national economies based on mutual compatibility and harmony of reproduction, rather than geographical location or level of development. If regionalization is considered horizontal integration, then TMK and MSG can be considered vertical integration. The role of international organizations such as the WTO, World Bank, and IMF is becoming increasingly important in the context of globalization.

As humanity continues to develop at a rapid pace, increasing the rate of production and further developing the economy cannot be achieved through national economic activity alone. Regional integration associations are also necessary. Another significant feature of the current era is the narrowing of the telecommunications space, and humanity is moving towards planetary reproduction. An example of this is the intercontinental BRICS association, which has emerged in recent years and is gaining global importance. The union is not bound by territorial, religious, linguistic, mental, or developmental proximity. The only criterion that unites them is the desire to ensure joint development in the future.

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